

A Machine Learning Approach to Investigate the Effects of Walking Speed on Gait Phase Sub-Durations via Biomarker-Driven Classification

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ABSTRACT:

An accurate understanding of gait phase sub-durations is essential for assessing and monitoring the rehabilitation progress of individuals with mobility impairments. This research investigates the influence of walking speed on the durations of major gait phases. It develops a machine learning model to predict the instantaneous phases using kinematic and kinetic data, which were derived from wearable biomarkers.

A dataset of 3D marker positions was employed from foot segments used to derive the position and velocity vectors and ground reaction force data, which were collected from individuals walking on a treadmill at a speed range of 0.6 m/s to 1.7 m/s. By examining the variation in gait sub-phase durations (i.e., loading response, mid-stance, terminal stance, pre-swing, and swing) across different speeds and analyzing their distributions and mean values, results showed that walking speed significantly changes the durations of gait phases, especially the relative contributions of stance and swing phases. Random forest and four other classifiers were trained to predict the instantaneous gait phase. The random forest model was able to achieve high accuracy in classifying the gait phases, with robust precision.

Our model's performance was evaluated using standard classification metrics and a confusion matrix. Feature importance analysis was also conducted to identify the most informative input signals. The result demonstrates the feasibility of predicting gait sub-durations using only biomarker-based kinematic and kinetic signals, providing a scalable approach to quantifying gait patterns under different speed conditions, an essential tool for clinical gait analysis and rehabilitation monitoring.

Keywords: Rehabilitation, Gait Phase, Machine Learning, Random Forest, Biomarkers, Sub-durations, Walking Speeds.

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INTRODUCTION

Gait analysis is a fundamental technique for clinical diagnostics, for the assessment of neuromuscular coordination, and for the identification of early signs of diseases such as stroke, Parkinson's, and other mobility-reducing disorders [1]. Popular tools that have been used in the research environment of gait evaluation include the two-dimensional and three-dimensional motion capture systems. These systems are used to record precise movements that enable the analysis of kinetic and kinematic aspects of gait with high accuracy. More methods are being explored due to advancements in technology to assess the best gait mechanics. One part of this gait analysis is focused on analysis of gait phase sub-durations, which are time intervals of the gait cycle, such as loading response, mid stance, terminal stance, pre-swing, and swing phases.

These sub-phases are indicative of the motor control and their deviations in timing, which may serve as an indicator of neuromuscular impairment (a condition that affects the nerves that control voluntary muscles and causes problems for the muscles to function properly, such problems include weakness, paralysis, or poor coordination) [2]. People who are undergoing a rehabilitation process after experiencing a stroke often have unbalanced coordination and symmetry of movement, which results in an abnormal timing of the gait phase. By measuring the differences in the gait phase sub-durations, one can objectively measure rehabilitation progress, implement the right therapeutic interventions, and detect deviations at an earlier stage. This can be done by understanding the effects of gait speed on biomechanical variables for proper evaluation of alterations in gait. The next process is to establish how the walking speed affects gait sub-phase durations of a healthy individual, which is crucial for clinical comparison and the development of personalized treatment methods [3].

Lanotte [1] and Khera [4] research shows that the advances in wearables and machine learning techniques can improve the resolution and practicality of gait analysis. The inertial measurement units (IMUs), 3D motion capture systems, and force plates are shown to allow continuous collection of kinematic and kinetic data while walking. Supervised machine learning algorithms like Random Forests and Support Vector Machines demonstrated high accuracy in classifying gait phases and detecting abnormal movements with accuracy over 90%. [4] The wearables have allowed us to perform non-invasive gait monitoring in clinical settings and at home, which enables one to identify motor impairments in the early stages of the disease for people recovering from stroke. [5]

Walking speed has been known to affect the temporal structure of the gait cycle. With increased walking speed, the stance phase usually becomes shorter, with the swing phase lengthening accordingly [3]. The knowledge of normative behaviors is therefore necessary to identify deviations due to pathological conditions. For instance, a slow and asymmetric gait pattern may indicate the presence of early-stage neurological conditions that may not be noticeable without analyzing gait phase sub-durations.

This study explores the correlation between different walking speeds and gait sub-phase durations of a healthy individual. It also develops a machine learning framework for gait phase classification using multi-modal biomechanical data. 3D kinematic data (position and velocity vectors) and ground reaction force data (force-rate derivatives) were collected from a subject walking at several speeds from 0.6 m/s to 1.7 m/s. A random forest classifier was developed to predict the current gait phase based on these features. The presented approach leverages wearables and intelligent classification algorithms to provide a scalable solution for real-time prediction of gait phases. This research contributes to the development of objective monitoring systems for early detection of strokes and personalized treatment planning.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Gait Sub-Phases as Biomarkers for Neurological Conditions

The sub-phases of gait have become an essential part of biomechanical analysis due to their ability to show subtle changes in neuromuscular control and coordination. Earlier approaches to gait

analysis were based on the entire stance and swing phases. Nowadays, gait has been segmented into loading response, mid-stance, terminal stance, pre-swing, and swing phases. These sub-phases provide a more granular view of timing variations and asymmetries that are crucial in the early detection of neurological dysfunctions. Abnormalities in gait subphases are the first signs of developing motor dysfunction, especially in post-stroke patients. According to Kim et al. [6], changes in sub-phase timing, especially those associated with changes in the ratio between the stance and swing phases, may also precede the occurrence of a stroke even before the onset of clinical signs. Thus, gait sub-phases are not only used as a marker for diagnosing neurological conditions but also as a prognostic factor for determining treatment plans.

The Significance of Gait Rehabilitation After Stroke

Gait rehabilitation is a key aspect of the recovery process after a stroke. Selves [7] points out that “early assessment of walking ability is important for informing the planning of treatment” (p. 160). Key predictors of walking after a stroke include trunk control and lower-limb motor function. Based on the TWIST algorithm, which is used in a clinical setting, the authors predicted ambulation ability within a week after a stroke. Furthermore, the 6MWT has been widely recognized for its ability to estimate endurance and mobility in terms of functionality. This makes it an important predictor of ambulation in the community. Types of gait rehabilitation modalities range from treadmill training to robotic-assisted rehabilitation and even circuit training to self-rehabilitation programs. Using gait sub-phases for analysis in the early stages of the rehabilitation process allows the detection of asymmetries and coordination issues that would otherwise go undetected, providing a more tailored intervention.

Wearable Technology for Gait Analysis

Wearable technology for monitoring gait is important because it makes gait analysis accessible outside the controlled environment of a laboratory. According to Prasanth [8], the systems used in the present time include IMUs (inertial measurement units), foot pressure sensors, and accelerometers. These devices allow for measuring “ground reaction forces and their derivatives” (p. 9) to estimate the heel strike and toe-off with high precision. One of the early pioneers in the development of such systems was Prasanth [8] with their wireless sensorized insoles. Nowadays, the research teams are developing hybrid biosensor systems, which incorporate 3D position tracking, velocity measurements, and the distribution of pressure to provide a continuous analysis of the gait cycle in an environment of free movement. The move towards wearable and portable devices is particularly important for long-term rehabilitation and allows clinicians to gather a lot of information to develop interventions for patients.

Machine Learning in Gait Phase Segmentation

Machine learning (ML) methods are now used in the analysis of gait because they can handle large amounts of data. Studies in the last issue of Munoz et al. [9] show that ML models, and specifically Random Forest (RF) classifiers followed by Support Vector Machine (SVM) with the causal inference model CIM, show a relation between leg variables and the arm swing asymmetry (ASA) and a proportional relationship between ASA and the diagnosis of PD with a robust estimator. RF methods are particularly efficient because they are based on an ensemble learning approach, which makes them less susceptible to overfitting and allows them to build their own features.

Ethical Issues in Continuous Gait Monitoring

There are many positive sides to continuous monitoring systems for gait. However, it should be noted that the monitoring process raises several ethical issues. Such devices are likely to breach patients’ privacy and raise concerns about patient autonomy. A. H. Seh [10] suggests that on-device processing is required to reduce the amount of data transmitted and limit the exposure to security breaches. Patients should also be given control over their data, including the right to opt in or out of the monitoring program. The ethics of the implementation of the devices are important because of the economic disparity that might arise between the groups of patients who have access to advanced monitoring equipment. It is important to note that the prolonged use of such devices can be harmful for certain patients, causing stress or compulsive behavior. Therefore, clear standards should be

established for the ethics of implementation to prevent any harm to the patient and respect their rights.

Gait Speed and Its Influence on Gait Phases

Gait speed is a key variable in gait sub-phases. The research by J. M. Yentes [11] on sample entropy revealed that lower speeds lead to less regularity and more variance in the stride pattern. It can be said that changes in the signal regularity are the proof of gait adaptability, but it also complicates the analysis of results. Some deviations in gait in a single velocity could actually be normal adaptive responses at that speed. Thus, the gait analysis should include walking at multiple speeds to determine true pathological deviations from the norm and differentiate between adaptive changes at different speeds. The research by Fukuchi et al. [3] supports the hypothesis that the normalized duration of the sub-phases at different speeds forms the basis for identifying deviations, especially in patients with disabilities in movement.

Gait as a Biomarker for Neurodegenerative Disorders

Gait analysis is becoming increasingly popular as a non-invasive biomarker for early detection of neurodegenerative disorders. Kim et al. [6] have demonstrated that changes in gait lead to cognitive impairment in the early stages of Alzheimer's disease (AD). Also, as Cicirelli et al. [12] explained, the changes in gait cycles often appear before the onset of neurologic symptoms. The authors provide an extensive review on how "temporal and spatial parameters of gait can reflect underlying neural deficits" (p. 142) of many neurodegenerative diseases such as Parkinson's and Alzheimer's disease. The gait cycle phases can be quantitatively assessed by using a technological tool to offer objective measurement of the various components and therefore a supplement to subjective clinical evaluation. It was further highlighted by Mancini and Horak [13] that "subtle changes in stance phase duration and swing symmetry correlate significantly with disease progression" (p. 87), suggesting that gait analysis can be a helpful method for identifying and tracking early neurodegeneration.

Challenges in Gait Biomechanics and Robotic Devices

Translating biomechanical knowledge into robotic applications is fraught with difficulties. A. R. Wu [14] highlights that powered lower-limb exoskeletons must navigate the complexity of human locomotion. The study shows that current robotic systems struggle to adapt to variations in walking speed and terrain, which restricts their real-world applicability. Additionally, Y. Liu [15] points out that the integration of user intent recognition with mechanical assistance requires sophisticated algorithms capable of real-time biomarker processing. These challenges are further exacerbated by the necessity for lightweight, energy-efficient designs that do not hinder natural movement patterns.

Improvements in Random Forest Algorithms for Gait Classification

Machine learning methods are also yielding improvements in gait classification. Shi et al. (2020) reports a fusion feature engineering operator and Random Forest (RF) classification that reports "an average accuracy of 98.2% across five different gait patterns". The FPRF-GR model operates to remove redundant features from the feature set through Fast Fourier Transform and principal component analysis. More of this type of algorithmic advance highlights the ways that machine learning can readily work with the complex biomechanical data produced from wearable IMUs.

Clinical Implications and Future Directions

The clinical utility of gait analysis is also in the development of individualized treatment plans based on a person's specific gait characteristics. H. Shi's [17] research explained that biomarker-driven classification of gait abnormalities enables targeted rehabilitation strategies. Therapeutic interventions can be tailored to address the specific impairments identified during the gait analysis and adjusted over time according to quantitative measures of outcome. Bloemendaal et al. [18] reported that speed-specific gait training improves functional outcomes more effectively than conventional approaches. This finding has important implications for the rehabilitation of individuals with mobility impairments. In the future, advances in artificial intelligence and wearable sensor technology are likely to make gait assessment more accessible and accurate.

METHODOLOGY

Data Acquisition and Preprocessing

The dataset used in this study was obtained from the Kaggle website (dasmehdixtr/human-gait-phase-dataset). This dataset comprises synchronized time-series data from 21 humans as subjects (10 males, 11 females in the age range of $23.8 \text{ yrs} \pm 3.3 \text{ yrs}$) performing gait at different treadmill speeds and 25306 steps were acquired in total.

The raw data includes measurements from:

1. Marker Positions which are 3D coordinates (x, y, z) of markers placed on key foot landmarks (FCC, FM1, FM2, FM5) for both left and right feet, with 8 Oqus cameras sampled at 200 Hz. These provide kinematic information about foot segment movement.
2. Ground Reaction Forces (GRF) which are 3D forces (x, y, z) from force plates (FP1, FP2), representing the kinetic interaction with the ground, sampled at 1000 Hz.
3. Overstep Events for timestamps marking gait cycle boundaries.

The data went through series of preprocessing steps to prepare it for analysis. The CSV files for marker data, force data, and overstep events were loaded and integrated. Marker velocities were computed as the first derivative of position data, and force derivatives were computed as the first derivative of force data to capture rates of change in these signals. The higher-frequency force data (1000 Hz) was resampled to match the marker data frequency (200 Hz) by taking every fifth sample. The preprocessed marker and force data were concatenated. Gait phases were labeled by dividing each gait cycle (defined by consecutive overstep events) into five standard sub-phases based on typical biomechanical proportions: Loading Response, Mid Stance, Terminal Stance, Pre Swing, and Swing. Each data sample within a cycle was assigned the corresponding phase label. Subject identifiers and walking speeds were retained.

Figure 1. Force vs Heel Movement

The plot above (i.e figure 1) shows the raw time-series of vertical ground reaction forces (FP_z) and vertical heel marker positions (_FCC_z). This visualization is crucial for understanding how these fundamental kinetic and kinematic signals vary over time during gait and how they relate to events like heel strike (marked by a drop in heel position and the initiation of vertical force) and toe-off.

Observing these profiles helps confirm that the raw data captures the expected characteristics of gait. This plot shows the raw time-series of vertical ground reaction forces (FP_z) and vertical heel marker positions (_FCC_z). The visualization allows investigation of basic kinetic and kinematic signal changes throughout gait motion while illustrating their connection to specific events such as heel strike (identified by heel position drop and vertical force commencement) and toe-off. Reviewing these profiles is important to verify that the raw data reflects the expected characteristics of gait. Observing these profiles helps confirm that the raw data captures the expected characteristics of gait.

Data Preprocessing

Marker Trajectories (FCC_z) (Figure 2): This graph shows the time course of the vertical (z) position of important body markers (like the heel, labeled FCC) with color representing the gait phase label identified in the preprocessing step. It provides a visual check on the quality of the automatically identified gait phases, confirming whether the labeled phases correspond to intuitive biomechanical events (e.g., ensuring that the 'Swing' phase is when the heel is indeed off the ground). This is crucial for ensuring the reliability of the subsequent steps, including duration analysis and model training.

Figure 2. FCC z-axis Trajectories

Gait Phase Labelling

Every sample got assigned to one of five detailed gait cycle segments.

The calculation of labels utilized proportional time progression measurements between detected oversteps. The subject ID and walking speed information was included with each sample.

Figure 3. Distribution of Gait Phases by Walking Speed

Figure 3 plot illustrates the total number of data samples (and thus, indirectly, the total accumulated duration) for each gait phase, categorized by walking speed. This plot provides an initial view of how the dataset is distributed across speeds and phases, highlighting which phases and speeds are most

represented in the data used for training and testing. It serves as a preliminary check on data balance across the different conditions studied.

The combined dataset, incorporating all preprocessed features and phase labels, was then used for model training and evaluation.

Feature Selection and Model Training

The features used for gait phase prediction included all preprocessed marker positions, marker velocities, ground reaction forces, and ground force derivatives. The target variable was the gait phase label. The data was splitted into 70% training and 30% testing sets, stratified by both gait phase and subject to ensure representation across classes and participants.

A Random Forest classifier was trained within a scikit-learn pipeline that included

StandardScaler for feature normalization and RandomForestClassifier with $n_estimatorso = 100$, with a random state of 1 to ensures that the random process of building trees can be regenerated to handle potential class imbalances.

RESULTS

Table 1. Evaluating Multiple Machine Learning Classifiers on GaitPhase (Marker & Force CSV Files) Dataset

Model Classifiers	Accuracy In Dataset	Accuracy In Percentage %
Support Vector Classifier (SVC)	0.9950	99.5
GaussianNB	0.9383	93.83
Decision Tress	0.9968	99.68
Random Forest	1.0000	100
Logistics Regression	0.9863	98.63
K neighbors	1.0000	100

After preprocessing and model training, the following results were obtained regarding gait phase durations and the performance of the gait phase classification model.

Gait Phase Duration Analysis

Analysis of the labeled data provided insights into the temporal characteristics of gait phases and how they are influenced by walking speed.

Figure 4. Distribution of Gait Phases Durations

Box plots(i.e figure 4) showed the distribution of individual instances of each gait phase duration across all subjects and speeds. This plot provided a summary of the typical range and variability for each phase's duration, confirming that certain phases (e.g., Mid Stance, Swing) generally have longer durations than others (e.g., Loading Response, Pre Swing). Boxplots demonstrate uniform patterns across subjects while showing shorter loading response and pre swing durations at faster speeds which confirms their ability to differentiate between classes.

Feature Correlation Analysis

The relationships between chosen marker and force-based features were assessed to determine hidden connections.

Figure 5 is a Feature Correlation Heatmap that illustrated the pairwise relationships between a subset of key features. This revealed which biomechanical signals were strongly correlated, providing context for understanding the feature space used by the model. For example, strong correlations might exist between vertical force and vertical marker position/velocity during certain parts of the gait cycle. Intra-group correlations appear robust within the heatmap (e.g., marker positions - velocities and force - derivatives) but gait events such as heel strike show unique connections between markers and force derivatives.

Figure 5. Feature Correlation Heat Map

Walking Speed vs Gait Phase

This analysis demonstrates the relationship between walking speed and the duration of individual gait sub-phases. Figure 6 demonstrated the direct relationship between walking speed and the mean duration of each gait phase. The results indicated that as walking speed increased, the mean duration of the stance phases (Loading Response, Mid Stance, Terminal Stance, Pre Swing combined, or individually) generally decreased. The Swing phase duration's relationship with speed was also evident, potentially showing a different rate of change compared to stance phases. This visualization provides quantitative evidence supporting the influence of walking speed on the temporal partitioning of the gait cycle into its sub-phases.

Figure 6. Gait Phase Duration vs. Walking Speed

Gait Phase Classification Model Performance

The trained Random Forest model's ability to classify instantaneous gait phases based on the chosen features was evaluated on the test set. The performance metrics are crucial because accurate instantaneous classification is necessary to derive reliable gait phase durations by aggregating consecutive predictions.

Classification Report (Output 11): The model achieved a high overall accuracy in classifying gait phases. Detailed metrics (precision, recall, F1-score) for each phase showed strong performance, particularly for the longer phases like Mid Stance and Swing. Metrics for shorter transition phases were also favorable, indicating the model's ability to capture the subtle signal changes during phase transitions.

Normalized Confusion Matrix

Figure 7. Normalized Confusion Matrix

This visually confirmed the model's strong performance, with the majority of predictions falling on the diagonal, indicating correct classification. The off-diagonal elements highlighted where misclassifications occurred, most often between temporally adjacent phases, which is common in gait analysis due to the continuous nature of movement transitions.

Our interpretability analysis utilized feature importance scores generated from the Random Forest model.

Top 20 Feature Importances

Feature Importance (Output 12, Figures 8 & 9): Random Forest analysis. The analysis of the biomarkers ranked according to the feature importance analysis. Features associated with vertical ground reaction forces (FP_z), its derivative (FP_z_diff) and vertical velocities (* z_vel) of the heel (FCC) and forefoot (FM1) marker were ranked at the top, emphasising their relevance for the recognition of gait phases and justifying the choice of using these biomarker-derived features for gait phase analysis. The plots of feature distribution and cumulative feature importance for the top features are also provided.

Conclusions. In conclusion, our findings support the influence of walking speed on gait phase durations. The Random Forest analysis demonstrated that vertical heel motion in combination with swing phase duration and force signal derivatives were the most informative features, reflecting their biomechanical significance. The high classification accuracy indicates that the combined use of marker position/velocity and force/force derivative information is adequate for identifying instantaneous gait phases, a necessary step for obtaining reliable sub-durations for subsequent analysis related to rehabilitation or other use cases.

The Random Forest analysis demonstrated that vertical heel motion in combination with swing phase duration and force signal derivatives were the most informative features, reflecting their biomechanical significance.

Figure 8. Top 20 Feature Importance

Figure 9. Top Feature Importance and Type

DISCUSSION

In this study, we attempted to understand how walking speed relates to gait phase sub-durations using wearable biomarker-derived kinematic and kinetic signals as inputs to phase classification. We found that walking speed does impact the distribution of the relative sub-phase durations of gait, as its variation results in a change of the relative stance-to-swing phase duration. This increase in speed shrank the overall gait cycle, with an average drop in stance phase and an increase in swing phase sub-phase. The reduction in stance phase is explained by a shift in biomechanics towards a shorter loading response and mid-stance, which are the result of a less time-consuming double-limb support [18]. These observations support current biomechanics literature as well as our assumption that a variability in walking speed should be captured when performing a clinical gait analysis. Using a dataset composed of 3D marker trajectories and ground reaction forces collected across a range of treadmill walking speeds (0.6–1.7 m/s), we derived velocity vectors and force features that were used as input to train several machine learning models.

Random Forest out of the five classifiers that we trained and tested provided the highest performance with near-perfect values for all metrics, including precision, recall, F1-score, and confusion matrix. It is also well-parameterized and generalized across various speed conditions for robustness. This shows that the instantaneous gait phase can be predicted under different walking speeds for clinical application. Feature importance further supported that the ground reaction forces, its derivative, and vertical heel and forefoot velocities were the top signals used to predict the instantaneous gait phase as a fraction of a gait cycle. It also shows that signals derived from these force and IMU sensors were used to separate sub-phases such as loading response, mid-stance, terminal stance, pre-swing, and swing. The ability to reconstruct these sub-phase durations from non-invasive, wearable biomarker signals provides a scalable, real-time solution for clinical gait analysis.

Our results are consistent with prior work in the field. Yan et al. [19] show that the gait speed directly affects time-distance parameters in gait analysis. They support the finding that the gait analysis at different walking speeds is essential for the inclusion of variability, especially when considering patients with a naturally slower cadence or motor impairments. Similar to this work, Özateş et al. [20] used machine learning and explainable AI to identify the most important features in gait classification. With KNN and Random Forest classifiers and near-perfect accuracy, the study used different ML

approaches to train and validate their prediction model. They then leveraged a feature importance technique to provide clarity on the optimal predictor features in the model that can be further translated to clinical environments. This also helped in their proposed method by providing a more interpretable model with data dimensionality reduction. Shah et al. [21] state that normal gait has a repeatable and predictable sequence of events that may be altered by pathology. Thus, recognizing the speed-dependent variability in gait timing is important to avoid the risk of misdiagnosis in the case of patients with lower or atypical walking speeds. Chan and Rudins [22] also found that normal gait consists of roughly 60% stance and 40% swing phases for an average pace and that the ratio changes significantly in the form of swing phases such as loading response as the walking speed varies. This work further illustrates the application of the clinical domain with engineering advances. The approach of Prasanth [23] indicates the possibility of using wearable sensor-based continuous gait monitoring in patients, highlighting IMU and rule-based methods as an optimal solution. Similarly, Evers et al. [24] verified the sensor-based real-world gait monitoring in Parkinson's disease, with good agreement with drug-response periods and motion variability. Such methods indicate the practicality and value of continuous gait analysis based on sensor measurements.

CONCLUSION

This research provides evidence that gait sub-phase durations can be accurately predicted using only kinematic and kinetic data from wearable sensors, without the need for complex or invasive setups. The use of random forest classifier also provided the best performance metrics and suited well for real-time gait phase recognition and use of the approach in real clinical settings. In summary, this research has provided a framework to capture how the gait sub-phase durations are dependent on walking speed by using wearable biomarkers and low-cost portable inertial measurement units. The integration of machine learning approaches with biomechanical domain knowledge can be used to further the field with significant clinical impact in the future. In conclusion, the proposed system for gait phase recognition using continuous sensor data with a combination of knowledge of biomarker systems and clinical application of bioengineering can provide value in a clinical context. It allows for a safe, non-invasive, and scalable setup that can be used by patients at home or in the clinic. The proposed system provides a basis for personalized treatment plans, telerehabilitation, early detection, and objective quantification of motor impairments in patients with neurological or musculoskeletal conditions.

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APPENDIX

- Dataset: GaitPhase (Marker & Force CSV Files) - <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/dasmehdixtr/human-gait-phase-dataset>
- Code: <https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1Q84L2I4IM9cbAOJFMbzIYmv3Bi3IFpmE>
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Figure 10

